

**IMPROVE ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION SKILLS BY USING ENGLISH
PHONETIC ALPHABET DRILLS IN EFL STUDENTS**

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Abstract: This study aims to investigate the improvement of EFL students' English pronunciation skills by using English Phonetic alphabet drills. The instruments used for collecting data were English phonetic alphabet drills, English phonetic alphabet collecting forms, observation and focus group interview questions. The data were analyzed both statistically and descriptively. The results showed that all students were able to pronounce English consonant and vowel sounds more accurately after applying English phonetic alphabet drills.

Keywords: English pronunciation, English phonetic drills, Pronunciation errors

English is an international language, which has recently played an important role in communication. English becomes an instrument for researching knowledge and information needed for a career. Therefore, it can be stated that speaking is the core of communication, and the most important component of speaking is pronunciation. Clear pronunciation will have effect on productive communication. Therefore, English pronunciation, including understanding the English phonological system is very essential for students learning English as a second language or a foreign language. Huwingz (2004) mentioned that pronunciation is important for speaking and listening in communication. Speakers need to pronounce clearly and correctly, and listeners must be able to analyze the speech that they heard according to phoneme and phonological system to interpret it correctly. Therefore, pronouncing consonant and vowel sounds correctly is a basic element of pronunciation.

Moreover, pronouncing words accurately assists students in learning new vocabulary easily and gain more confidence in communication. For teaching English, Tauycharoen (2001) stated that learning vocabulary and structure is not enough for communication if students cannot pronounce the sounds that native speaker is able to understand. However, English pronunciation is one of the problems of students due to the English phonological systems. Some students do not understand the connections of unfamiliar letters, and sounds and cause them to miss pronunciation. Therefore, it is important and necessary to teach students how to pronounce correctly and understand the meaning of vocabulary (Torat,2004). The study of Nokaew and Suksri (2005) showed that the phonic teaching is a form of language learning by learning the letter – sound correspondence, which has related phonemes. Weaver (1994) said that phonic teaching allows people to learn the character or symbol of each voice before actually reading it in the context of the written language and encourages awareness of the differences of sounds in each word.

In addition, having phonetic knowledge helps learners to acquire knowledge about speech organs, and places of articulation to make the English sounds accurate. The more students can understand and pronounce the words phonetically correctly, the more likely they can pronounce English similarly to native speakers. As a result, students have confidence in their pronunciation. This makes communication more effective (Ruslansamae & Premin Karawi, 2015; Kulachit & Nuangchalerm, 2021). Learning pronunciation or having phonetics knowledge may be tools to practice the appropriate pronunciation. Therefore, research is aimed at studying the improvement of English pronunciation skills of students in English for International Communication major. This study is also focused on developing pronunciation skills by using English phonetic alphabet drills to help them pronounce English correctly and effectively. The objective of the study is to investigate how English alphabet drills aid improvement of students' English pronunciation skills and to be a guideline for improving students' English pronunciation.

English spelling is quite confusing because there is no one – to – one correspondence between the sounds that students hear and the letters that students see. That is, the English spelling system fails to represent the sounds of English. The inconsistency between spelling and sounds poses issues for number of reasons (Kanaksillapatham, 2015). For instance, the vowel sounds in words **see**, **sea**, **me**, **people**, **receive** and **field** are represented by one phonetic symbol /i/. It shows that they are the same vowel sound. Meanwhile, the “s” letter in the word **sun**, **measure**, and **design** is represented by three different sounds, /s/, /z/, and /z/.

Fu and Aonsawat (2006) stated that the complexity of the sound creation process is different between a language with a compels writing system and an uncomplicated writing system. Yim-on (2014) pointed out that studying the phonetic alphabet will help students break an incorrect correspondence between a letter and sound, and it helps students know the right pronunciation of the words they have to speak out. Moreover, having knowledge about phonetic alphabet will students correct their English mistakes.

CONCLUSION

This study applied English phonetic alphabet drills to improve students’ English consonant and vowel pronunciation. The result showed that students were able to pronounce English consonants and vowel more accurately after applying the drills, but the nasal sound in final position, and the lateral sound in the initial and the medial position were still the problematic sounds. Moreover, students should pay attention to their pronunciation learning strategies. For English vowel sounds, central and back vowels were the problematic sounds for students. Improving English pronunciation has to take time to see obvious changes, so we suggest the researchers should be concerned about the duration of the study in this field, including instruments in the study. It was clear that students had difficulties pronouncing voiced sounds. Therefore, to improve English pronunciation especially consonant and vowel is important to have an appropriate way.

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